

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF TRADITIONAL AND DISTANCE LEARNING

Oltinbekova Dilxumor Oltinbek qizi

Uzbekistan state world languages university

Abdusamadov Zafar Nurmatovich

Uzbekistan state world languages university

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Abstract. *This article compares two forms of learning: traditional and distance. The authors give specific information about advantages and disadvantages of both ways of learning.*

Keywords: *learning, advantages, disadvantages, traditional, distance, education.*

ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА И НЕДОСТАТКИ ТРАДИЦИОННОГО И ДИСТАНЦИОННОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ

Аннотация. *В данной статье сравниваются две формы обучения: традиционная и дистанционная. Авторы дают конкретную информацию о преимуществах и недостатках обоих способов обучения.*

Ключевые слова: *обучение, преимущества, недостатки, традиционное, дистанционное, обучение.*

INTRODUCTION

As we all know, getting an education today is not difficult. Some students manage to combine business with pleasure: studying at a university and at the same time working at an enterprise. As a rule, the first higher education (bachelor's degree) is received internally, and the mastering of the remaining degrees (master's, graduate student, etc.) takes place in parallel with work. Recently, people have begun to show particular interest in distance learning.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Distance learning is one of the options for the educational process at a distance. The interaction of teachers and students takes place using modern means of communication: computers, webcams, video materials, mail, etc. The quality of such education is in no way inferior to full-time or part-time education. The student is also given lecture material for study, he independently studies a certain volume of the course, performs a number of verification works (tests, control and coursework, writes a thesis project). The term "distance learning" covers a wide range of programs and courses aimed at acquiring new knowledge and skills, retraining personnel, and using online seminars, webinars, videoconferences, etc.

RESULTS

How did distance learning come about?

In the late 1980s, scientific progress began to actively develop. New equipment and means of communication have appeared in the country, which simplify the process of interaction between people: new ways of transferring information, satellite communications have appeared. In fact, science has allowed humanity to overcome the "distance barrier": it became possible to communicate and receive services from different parts of the planet.

Now, thanks to Internet technologies, a person not only communicates, but also receives an education or develops his own business, without leaving home. Even 20-30 years ago, they could not even think about it.

The first university to offer distance learning opened in 1969 in the UK. In Russia, such programs began operating much later - in 1997.

DISCUSSION

It is important to keep up with the times: to constantly develop, learn, master new technologies and put them into practice. Distance education helps to achieve success.

And we all know that the undoubted advantage of traditional education is the ability to convey a large amount of information in a short time. With such training, students acquire knowledge in a ready-made form without revealing ways of proving its truth. Among the significant disadvantages of this type of learning is its focus more on memory than on thinking. This training also contributes little to the development of creativity, independence, activity. The educational and cognitive process is largely reproductive (reproducing) in nature, as a result of which the reproductive style of cognitive activity is formed in students. In addition, there is no opportunity to adapt the pace of learning to the various individual psychological characteristics of students (the contradiction between frontal learning and the individual nature of the assimilation of knowledge).

A characteristic feature of traditional education is its appeal to the past, to those treasuries of social experience, where knowledge is stored, organized in a specific form of educational information. Hence the orientation of learning to memorize the material. It is assumed that as a result of training as a purely individualized process of assigning information, the latter acquires the status of knowledge. [2] In this case, information, a sign system acts as the beginning and end of the student's activity, and the future is presented only in the form of an abstract perspective of the application of knowledge.

It is useful to differentiate more strictly between the concepts of "information" and "knowledge". Information in teaching is a certain sign system (for example, text of a textbook, speech of a teacher) that exists objectively, outside of a person. One or another sign as a carrier of information in a certain way replaces real objects, and this is the advantage of using information in teaching. Through substitute signs, the learner can economically and quickly master reality.

CONCLUSIONS

Summing up the above, we can say that in the conditions of the content and structure of modern education, the development of traditional education, therefore, the abilities of students takes on a new meaning and requires further comprehension and improvement. The best results can be achieved only with an optimal combination of different types of training.

Undoubtedly, traditional education has firmly entered our educational system and gives its results, which depend on the individual psychological characteristics of the child.

First of all, it should be noted that despite the words of experts and specialists from pedagogy, the concept of "better" or "worse" is always subjective. This means that "better" for some may not necessarily be the same for you. Among other things, the particular school with which the comparison is made, its advantages and disadvantages, are of serious importance.

However, it is possible to compare the training systems themselves, based on existing experience to give their assessment. In comparing the two systems, we will rely on four criteria, the first of which is: The understanding and interpretation of effectiveness is very different, we will rely on the volume and totality of knowledge and skills that students receive during classes.

According to this indicator, distance learning is in the lead. The secret of this approach lies in the ability to create a flexible and individualized program for each student. In a traditional school, in the classroom, this is not possible. Even household chores are assessed and checked in a fairly uniform way. When working remotely with students, much more productive communication is built: consultations on all emerging issues, assistance in developing a complex topic, additional information on the chosen direction, etc. In addition, the traditional school is quite "traditional", many innovations are perceived negatively by the administration and inspection bodies. At the same time, the modern school curriculum is subject to serious criticism as outdated and insufficient even for admission to a domestic university. Distance learning at school from the very beginning assumes a more flexible approach, it can include a much larger amount of material. The meaning of "working time" and "teaching hours", on the basis of which teachers are paid in a traditional school, have been significantly revised here. All this helps to give the student more remotely, to help him better understand the entire program, to demonstrate the best results at any level.

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